

CONTINUOUS REASONING ABOUT PRESCHOOL EDUCATION AND UPBRINGING

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Abstract. *One of the most important directions of further development of preschool education is the widespread introduction of modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies into the educational process.*

The creation of conditions for the comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of preschool children requires a revision of the existing order of organization of the educational process in preschool educational organizations and the introduction of modern methods of providing preschool education services. The content of intellectual and educational games reflects the world of children's fairy tales, cartoons, therefore attracts the attention and interest of the child, forms a playful mood, a desire to join the training.

Keywords: *training, education, preschool education, intellectual and developmental games, formation, optimization, development, lesson, elementary, presentation.*

Continuing education is understood as the connection, consistency and perspective of all components of the system (goals, objectives, content, methods, means, forms of organization of education and training) at each stage of education to ensure continuity in the development of the child.

The idea of continuity of education is currently more declared than implemented, which actualizes the task of creating a concept that reveals modern approaches to the goals and content of continuing education at its first stages – preschool and primary school[1].

The concept is based on the values of education recognized in modern pedagogy:

- humanism as the affirmation of the norms of respect for the human person, benevolent and careful attitude towards everyone; exclusion of coercion and violence;
- human openness to the changing world;
- self-worth of each age: full realization of the child's capabilities; reliance on the achievements of the previous stage of development - unjustifiability both in the infantilization of education and "getting ahead";
- individualization of education: taking into account the abilities, interests, and pace of advancement of the child;
- creating conditions for its development, regardless of the level of initial preparedness.

The concept of continuing education (preschool and primary education) is designed to:

- to identify priorities in the content of education at each of these stages of age development, taking into account the current social situation;
- to determine the psychological and pedagogical conditions for the implementation of the continuity of education;
- identify the contribution of each educational area to the development of preschool and primary school children;

Psychological and pedagogical conditions for the implementation of continuing education [2].

The realization of the common goal and objectives of the education of children of these ages requires compliance with a number of psychological and pedagogical conditions:

- personality-oriented interaction of adults with children;
- providing each child with the opportunity to choose an activity, partner, funds, etc.;
- orientation of pedagogical assessment on relative indicators of children's success (comparison of today's achievements of the child with his own yesterday's achievements);
- creating an educational environment conducive to the emotional and value, social and personal, cognitive, aesthetic development of the child and the preservation of his individuality;
- formation of the leading activity as the most important factor in the development of the child; reliance on the game in the formation of educational activities;
- the balance of reproductive (reproducing a finished sample) and research, creative activity, joint and independent, mobile and static norms of activity.

The following basic concepts apply in this Law:

children with special educational needs — children with individual needs, regardless of whether there is a disability or not, requiring special attention of the family, teachers, specialists, society and the state;

state preschool educational organization — an organization financed and managed by the state and providing preschool educational and upbringing services in accordance with the state standard of preschool education and upbringing;

inclusive education and upbringing — a process that ensures equal access for children to education and upbringing, taking into account their special educational needs and individual capabilities;

preschool age — the age of children from birth to seven years, until the moment of providing him with education in organizations of general secondary education;

preschool education and upbringing — a type of lifelong education aimed at educating and raising children, their intellectual, spiritual, moral, ethical, aesthetic and physical development, as well as preparing children for general secondary education;

the state standard of preschool education and upbringing — a set of mandatory requirements for the volume, content and quality of the educational process, the construction and equipment of a preschool educational organization, as well as the organization of healthy nutrition and safety of preschool children;

state educational program of preschool education and upbringing — a document that determines the volume and content of basic knowledge, skills and abilities to be acquired by the child, as well as characterizing the specifics of the content of education and upbringing, especially the organization of the educational process;

preschool educational organization — a state and non-governmental organization that provides educational and educational services in the field of preschool education and upbringing;

non-governmental preschool educational organization — a legal entity providing educational and upbringing services in the field of preschool education and upbringing on the basis of a license to carry out activities in the provision of non-state educational services[3].

Thus, the preschool education system is a flexible, multifunctional network of preschool educational institutions (pre-school) that provide a wide range of educational services, taking into account the age and individual characteristics of the child, the needs of the family and society as a whole. Preschool institutions are developing with the priorities of one or more areas of work with

children (compensatory kindergartens, supervision and rehabilitation, child development centers, etc.) [10].

In the conditions of continuous education, the pre-university educational content has to become an introduction to modern science. Only with such an approach can a genuine, professionally oriented education be possible. Acquaintance with the choice of profession has to be carried out not at the last stage of pre-university education, but during the whole period of this education, starting with kindergarten. Unfortunately, the symbolical informative level of the submission of educational information does not allow this. For this reason, symbolical cognitive information represents a spiral, which is developed in a symbolical field, expanding it in the process of the age development of the personality.

With such an approach, each age educational stage represents one autonomous region of the educational content. Similar isolation of separate age stages creates a condition of subsidiary of the previous age stage for the subsequent one. It is clear that the specified approach requires social and pedagogical control: someone will constantly have to lead the pupil along the educational spiral. As a result, we see that the source of informative development is not within the personality, but outside.

The principle of humanity testifies an educational orientation to the person, to the freedom of a person's choice in forms, terms, types of training, professional development, and self-education. This principle is realized through the creation of favorable opportunities for the development of a creative identity of each person. The person is considered as the purpose of the public progress. The principle of democracy assumes the availability of education at any age, due to a variety of forms of education, according to their interests, opportunities and requirements. It provides freedom of transition from one educational institution to another, accelerated completion of training and professional development; means the equal rights of all citizens, irrespective of their class position, national features, state of health, education and development. The principle of mobility is expressed in a variety of means, ways, and organizational forms of the system of continuous education, and their flexibility and readiness for fast reorganization according to the changing requirements of production, society and a person. It focuses on the use of different productive methodical systems and technologies [7].

The principle of advancing, of relying on scientific forecasting, demands faster and flexible development, reorganization of educational institutions and establishments of system of continuous education in relation to needs of public practice, and mobile updating of their activity. This principle focuses on a wide and active use of new forms, methods, tutorials and retraining of experts, on the inclusion of innovative approaches to this process. The principle of openness of the system of continuous education requires that the educational institutions expand their activity by attraction to training and professional development of nonconventional audiences, and free listeners.

Thus, there is a need to work with different age strata and groups of the population which differ in educational level and vocational training, in attitude to education, vital aspirations that requires the creation of additional faculties, institutes, offices, courses on improvement of education and qualification, holding seminars and leisure-time clubs, not only in the educational institution, but also beyond its limits, and also the organizations of television and video programs.

The principle of the continuity of education is a systematizing one. Educational institutions, educationalists and specialists in professional development, sciences and productions have to

reconsider a view on the role and place of education in human lives and societies. It is necessary to overcome the orientation to superficial "polyhistory" of the contents, and the overload by information and factual material. In the content of education, the problems of development of society, production, science, and culture must be reflected. Education has to be directed to the future. The offered system of the principles of continuous education is not exhaustive, and over time it will be complemented, taking into account new requirements, and new turns in the development of education

New forms of service for preschoolers have emerged (mini-gardens, short-term maintenance groups, walking, wellness, etc.). Educational institutions "primary school – kindergarten" have proven themselves positively, creating the most favorable conditions for ensuring continuity in the upbringing, education and development of children. Positive changes have been outlined in the formation and dissemination of psychological services for preschool and primary school children and their parents.

Significant changes have taken place in the content of education of preschool and primary school children, in the general nature and style of the pedagogical process: the variability of programs, curricula, and teaching tools is becoming increasingly widespread, which significantly enriches the content of both preschool and primary education. There has been a rejection of strictly regulated forms of education, the pedagogical community has accepted the ideas of humanistic pedagogy [8].

Analysis of the situation shows that this trend should remain a characteristic feature of the education system in the future. At the same time, the changes taking place in the education system have shown the unwillingness of a significant part of the teaching staff to consciously choose a variable educational program and its adequate implementation, taking into account the capabilities and needs of children. In addition, variability has brought an unjustified passion for subject learning to preschool education, and one—hour subjects to primary school, which has led to an unjustified increase in the requirements for entering school, a decrease in the quality of education and overload of children. The absence of education standards approved at the state level significantly hinders ensuring continuity and prospects in the education system[9].

Thus, preparation for school is often considered as an earlier study of the first-grade program and is reduced to the formation of narrow-subject knowledge and skills. In this case, the continuity between preschool and primary school age is determined not by whether the future student has developed the qualities necessary for the implementation of a new educational activity, whether its prerequisites have been formed, but by the presence or absence of certain knowledge in academic subjects. However, numerous studies by psychologists and educators show that the presence of knowledge in itself does not determine the success of learning, it is much more important that the child is able to independently extract and apply them. Therefore, the leading goal of preparing for school should be the formation of the qualities of a preschooler necessary for mastering educational activities – curiosity, initiative, independence, arbitrariness, creative self-expression of the child, etc.

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